

Complex Compounds of Rhenium with 2,2'-Dipyridyl

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The preparation and properties of cationic and nonelectrolytic pentavalent rhenium complexes with pyridine, viz., $[\text{ReO}_2\text{Py}_4]\text{Cl}$ and $\text{ReOPy}_2\text{Cl}_3$, have been described in previous communications¹. In the tetravalent state also, rhenium is known² to form a nonelectrolytic complex RePy_2Cl_4 with pyridine. In the present communication, the preparation and the properties of analogous complexes with 2,2'-dipyridyl are described.

2,2'-Dipyridylium hexachlororhenate(IV), $(\text{diPyH})_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$, was prepared according to the method of Morgan and Davies³. This greenish white substance was heated in a current of dry nitrogen at 220° when 2,2'-dipyridyl and hydrogen chloride were evolved and a yellow residue was obtained. This was washed successively with water, ethanol, and acetone and dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 (conc.). Analysis corresponded to the formula $\text{Re}(\text{diPy})\text{Cl}_4$. [Found: Re, 37.5; Cl, 29.3; N, 5.6; C, 25.6; H, 1.8. $\text{Re}(\text{diPy})\text{Cl}_4$ requires Re, 38.4; Cl, 29.3; N, 5.8; C, 24.8; H, 1.6%]. The same substance was also obtained by heating $(\text{diPyH})_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ in a current of air at 220°.

Tetrachloro-2,2'-(dipyridyl)rhenium is a yellow amorphous substance, insoluble in water and ethanol. It is very slightly soluble in acetone. This is an exceptionally stable compound and a suspension of the compound in H_2SO_4 (dil.) is not oxidised by dichromate even on prolonged digestion on a water bath. The substance is paramagnetic and the magnetic moment at 26° is 3.5 B.M., the magnetic moment of the analogous pyridine compound being 3.3 B.M.².

When a suspension of $(\text{diPyH})_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ in 0.4 N-HCl was refluxed in a current of air, an intense violet substance settled down. After prolonged reflux, it was filtered hot, washed successively with hot 0.4 N-HCl, ethanol, and acetone and dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 (conc.). Analysis of the substance and the determination of the oxidation state of rhenium by chromate oxidation corresponded to the formulation $\text{Re}^{\text{V}}\text{O}(\text{diPy})\text{Cl}_3$. [Found: Re, 39.7; N, 6.2; Cl, 22.1; $\text{ReO}(\text{diPy})\text{Cl}_3$ requires Re, 40.1; N, 6.0; Cl, 22.9%].

The substance forms intense violet microcrystals, insoluble in water and in common organic solvents.

By replacing 0.4N-HCl in the above preparation with strong (6N) HCl, a green substance of the same composition, $\text{ReO}(\text{diPy})\text{Cl}_3$, was obtained. The substance is insoluble

1. Chakravorti, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 81, 1045.

2. Tronev and Babeshkina, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1958, 3, 2458.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1868.

in water, but soluble in acetone and nitrobenzene and sparingly soluble in ethanol. It can be crystallised from the acetone solution. In both the solvents (acetone and ethanol) the absorption maxima of the green substance occur in the same regions, at 450 m μ in the visible region and at 288 and 235 m μ in the UV region. This is diamagnetic at room temperature. The violet and the green varieties appear to be *cis-trans* isomers.

By refluxing a mixture of the green $\text{ReO}(\text{diPy})\text{Cl}_3$ with excess of 2,2'-dipyridyl in ethanol, an intense blue-violet solution was obtained from which a blue-violet substance was precipitated with ether. Preliminary investigations show it to be a cationic complex of the probable composition $[\text{ReO}_2(\text{diPy})_2]\text{Cl}$.

Further study on the 2,2'-dipyridyl compounds and the isolation of analogous 1,10-phenanthroline compounds are in progress, details of which will be published elsewhere.

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